

Shared anchors for floating wind turbines

Test SW_03

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1 Introduction

This data report presents the experimental results from test SW_03, conducted on 17 December 2024. The centrifuge experiment included one monotonic loading test and two multidirectional loading tests on suction anchors embedded in normally consolidated clay.

2 General Information

The experiment involved testing three suction anchors installed in normally consolidated clay. The test sequence included a monotonic loading scenario followed by two multidirectional loading tests to assess the influence of load directionality on anchor capacity. The soil profile was prepared using Speswhite kaolin and reconstituted through consolidation under predefined pressures, as detailed in the following sections.

This experiment was carried out as part of the ShareWind project: Shared Anchors for Floating Wind Turbines (Grant agreement 101106921 – <https://doi.org/10.3030/101106921>).

3 Model Preparation

The experiment was conducted in a circular container with a diameter of 895 mm and a height of 700 mm. The clay bed was prepared by consolidating four layers of Speswhite kaolin, each subjected to different consolidation pressures. The kaolin was mixed with water to reach an initial water content of approximately 90% across all layers. Table 1 lists the target consolidation pressures used to simulate a normally consolidated clay profile. For the calculations, the

total unit weight γ was set to 16.6 kN/m^3 , and the effective unit weight γ' to 6.5 kN/m^3 . A scale factor of $N = 75$ between the prototype and the model was assumed (Fig. 1).

Table 1: Consolidation pressures and clay layers thickness - Model SW03

	Model			Prototype				Model and Prototype
	From (mm)	To (mm)	Thickness (mm)	From (m)	To (m)	Thickness (m)	Average Depth (m)	Average vertical stress (kPa)
Layer 4	0.0	95.0	95.0	0.0	7.1	7.1	3.6	23.5
Layer 3	95.0	180.0	85.0	7.1	13.5	6.4	10.3	68.1
Layer 2	180.0	260.0	80.0	13.5	19.5	6.0	16.5	108.9
Layer 1	260.0	335.0	75.0	19.5	25.1	5.6	22.3	147.3
		Total	335		Total	25.1		

Figure 1: Vertical effective stress profile for the clay

Before placing the first clay layer, a 90 mm thick sand layer was added at the base of the model to facilitate drainage during consolidation. The consolidation pressures were applied using a hydraulic piston equipped with a digital control system to regulate the applied loads. Figure 2 shows the loading system and the installation process of one of the clay layers in the container.

Table 2 summarizes the initial and final thicknesses of the reconstituted clay layers after consolidation under the target pressure range. The initial pressure applied to all layers was 6.9 kPa, corresponding to the self-weight of the hydraulic press.

Figure 2: Setup for the consolidation of the clay

Table 2: Consolidation of clay layers and loading sequence

Layer	H0 - Initial Height (mm)	Hf - Final Height (mm)	Hf/H0	Load Sequence (kPa)
Clay 4 (Top)	121	95	0.79	6.9 - 24
Clay 3	120	85	0.71	6.9 - 14 - 28 - 68
Clay 2	120	80	0.67	6.9 - 14 - 28 - 56 - 109
Clay 1 (Bottom)	115	75	0.65	6.9 - 14 - 28 - 56 - 112 - 147
Total	476	335		

4 Experimental setup

A prototype suction anchor with a diameter (D) of 4.5 m and a length (L) of 15.0 m, giving a length-to-diameter ratio (L/D) of 3.3, was selected. A centrifuge scaling factor of $N=75$ was used to allow testing of three model suction anchors within a single consolidated clay sample. Each anchor was equipped with three padeyes, positioned at approximately two-thirds of the anchor length from the top, to apply inclined loads from three mooring lines. Table 3 shows the model and prototype dimensions used in the centrifuge test.

Table 3: Prototype and model dimensions

Dimension	Model (1/75)	Prototype
Suction anchor		
Material	Stainless steel	–
D (diameter)	60 mm	4.5 m
L (length)	200 mm	15.0 m
L/D	3.3	3.3
t (wall thickness)	0.41 mm	3.0 cm
D/t	150	150
W (weight)	330.0 g	1.39 MN
W' (buoyant weight)	277.2 g	1.14 MN
Model Container		
Height	700 mm	52.5 m
Diameter	895 mm	67.1 m
Water table	50 mm	3.75 m
Soil layers		
Clay 4 (Top)	95 mm	7.1 m
Clay 3	85 mm	6.3 m
Clay 2	80 mm	6.0 m
Clay 1 (bottom)	75 mm	5.6 m

Figure 3 shows the experimental setup used in the centrifuge test. The setup included fixed components (parts No. 1 to No. 7 in Figure 3b) to support the actuators, pulleys, cameras, and laser sensors, as well as movable components such as the mooring lines and anchors. Three electric actuators (Figure 3a) were used to apply the loads. Each actuator was instrumented with a TME load cell with a 5 kN capacity. An extension piece (part No. 8) was attached to the top of each anchor. It consisted of an aluminium pipe and a 3D-printed circular cap, allowing additional measurements of anchor rotation, vertical displacement, and translation.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for multiline anchor testing

4.1 Suction Anchor Installation

The anchors were installed at 1-g by manually pushing them into the clay to their full length (200 mm). During installation, the top valves remained open to allow air to escape from the caisson (Figure 4a and 4c). To ensure vertical alignment, a guide made from an aluminium pipe was used. This guide could be removed by unscrewing it from the anchor's top cap. A 3D-printed support piece (Figure 4b) was attached to the main top plate (part No. 2 in Figure 3) to maintain the anchor's verticality during insertion.

Figure 4: Detail of a model anchor and installation at 1g

During anchor installation, the mooring lines were manually pretensioned to cut through the surrounding clay and establish a consistent starting point for load application. This ensured that all three lines exited the clay surface at the same location. After achieving this configuration, the pretension was released. Figure 5 shows an anchor following 1-g installation, including the footprint left by the mooring lines during pretensioning.

To ensure proper alignment of the lines within the pulleys, 3D-printed components referred to as stop cables were used (part No. 6 in Figure 2). The mooring lines consisted of 4 mm diameter SK78 Dyneema synthetic ropes. These cables have a Young’s modulus between 108 and 113 GPa (Vlasblom, 2018), a linear weight of approximately 9 g/m, and a load resistance of 1300 daN at 1% elongation (LIROS, 2025).

Figure 5: A view of a model anchor and instrumentation after installation at 1-g

4.2 Model Instrumentation

The centrifuge model was instrumented as follows. Druck pore pressure transducers (PPTs) were embedded during clay consolidation at three depths: (i) one anchor diameter (1D) below the caisson base, (ii) at the caisson base, and (iii) at the caisson top (Figure 6a). Surface settlements of the clay were measured using LVDTs.

Lateral displacements of the anchors were monitored using Baumer OM20 linear laser transducers. These sensors were configured to detect the centre of cylindrical objects within their measurement range. Two lasers arranged perpendicularly enabled tracking of the anchor extension’s motion in the horizontal (x–y) plane (Figure 6b). Additional Baumer OM20 point lasers were placed above the model to record vertical displacements at the top of the extension and estimate anchor rotations based on their relative distance (Figure 6c).

Figure 6: Model instrumentation. a) Lateral view of an anchor and connection of one mooring line. b) Linear lasers position to track lateral displacements. c) Point lasers to track vertical displacements and detail of an ArUco marker

To obtain additional displacement data via digital image correlation (DIC), an ArUco marker (Garrido et al., 2014) was placed on the upper extension of the anchor (Figure 6c). A camera (IP network camera HDI-47) mounted above the anchors enabled tracking of the marker's displacement, primarily within a planar projection.

5 Centrifuge Testing Programme

The anchor testing programme was carried out over three days, with one day allocated to each anchor. The testing conditions are summarized in Table 4.

The first anchor was tested under a monotonic inclined load (45°) to establish a baseline capacity. Additional monotonic loads were then applied through the other two mooring lines to evaluate the response under large displacements (Figure 7).

The second anchor was subjected to a series of monotonic load tests with increasing amplitudes, applied alternately between two mooring lines (Figure 8).

The third anchor was tested using simultaneous and alternating loads applied by two actuators (Figure 9).

Table 4: Identification of loading tests for the suction anchors

Anchor	Load condition	Loading rate (model scale)
1	Monotonic	30 mm/min
2	Multidirectional alternated	30 mm/min
3	Multidirectional two lines alternated	30 mm/min

Figure 7: Anchor 1: monotonic load sequence

Figure 8: Anchor 2: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by one mooring line

Figure 9: Anchor 3: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by two mooring lines simultaneously

For the simultaneous load tests a pre-load of approximately 5% of the anchor's ultimate capacity was applied to the two targeted mooring lines to ensure they remained taut, while the third line was kept slack. After the target load was applied, the mooring lines were unloaded. A schematic representation of a bidirectional load sequence is provided in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Anchor 3: detail of application of simultaneous load by two actuators

6 Test chronology

The centrifuge test was carried out in three stages that took place in three consecutive days as follows:

- Day 1 (*17-December-2025*): monotonic load test on anchor 1.
- Day 2 (*18-December-2025*): multidirectional alternated load test on anchor 2.
- Day 3 (*19-December-2025*): multidirectional with two lines alternated on anchor 3.

6.1 Anchor 1 - Monotonic Load Test

The monotonic load test involved applying inclined loads at an angle of 45° relative to the horizontal. The mooring line was connected to padeyes located at $2/3$ of the anchor's length, and the load was applied at a rate of 30 mm/min (0.5 mm/s). The test sequence was as follows:

- **08:00-10:00**: Test pre-checks, counterbalance calculation, verification of the response of the instruments.
- **10:00**: Data acquisition initiated at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **10:00**: Centrifuge test commenced.
- **10:15**: Centrifuge reached the target testing level of 75g.
- **10:15–15:15**: Re-consolidation phase for the clay.
- **15:15**: Data acquisition for the load tests restarted at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **15:17**: Mooring line 1 loaded, reaching a force of approximately 700 N (model scale).
- **15:22**: Mooring line 2 loaded, reaching a force of approximately 600 N (model scale).
- **15:30**: Mooring line 3 loaded, reaching a force of approximately 600 N (model scale).
- **15:46**: T-bar test performed with data acquisition at 100 Hz. A technical issue occurred with the load cell of the device.
- **15:55-16:05**: Centrifuge swing-down and end of the test.

6.2 Anchor 2 - Multidirectional Alternated Load Test

The multidirectional alternated load test involved applying inclined loads at an angle of 45° relative to the horizontal, with the mooring lines connected to padeyes located at $2/3$ of the anchor's length. The loads were applied at a rate of 30 mm/min (0.5 mm/s) in an alternating sequence with increasing amplitudes, as illustrated in Figure 8. After the application of the load packages, a monotonic load test was conducted. The test sequence proceeded as follows:

- **08:00–10:00**: Pre-test checks, including counterbalance calculations and verification of instrument response.
- **10:37**: Data acquisition initiated at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **10:37**: Centrifuge test commenced.

- **10:45:** Centrifuge reached the target testing level of 75g.
- **10:45–15:45:** Re-consolidation phase for the clay.
- **15:46:** Data acquisition for the load tests restarted at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **15:46–16:30:** Load tests conducted on the anchors. Mooring Line 2 was loaded first, followed by Line 3 and then Line 1.
- **16:45:** T-bar test performed with data acquisition at 100 Hz.
- **16:50–17:05:** Centrifuge swing-down and conclusion of the test.

6.3 Anchor 3 - Multidirectional Loading with Alternating Lines

This test involved the simultaneous application of monotonic loads through two mooring lines inclined at 45° relative to the horizontal. The mooring lines were connected to padeyes located at two-thirds of the anchor’s length. The loading rate was set to 30 mm/min (0.5 mm/s), with progressively increasing amplitudes, as illustrated in Figure 9.

- **09:00–09:40:** Pre-test checks, including counterbalance calculations and verification of instrument response.
- **09:40:** Data acquisition initiated at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **09:40:** Centrifuge test commenced.
- **09:55:** Centrifuge reached the target acceleration level of 75g.
- **09:55–15:55:** Re-consolidation phase of the clay.
- **15:55:** Data acquisition for the load tests resumed at a sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- **15:55–17:30:** Execution of load tests on the anchor:
 - Load lines 1 and 2 to $0.2F_{ult} = 140$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 2 to 25 N. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 2. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 2 and 3 to $0.2F_{ult} = 140$ N. Preload actuators 2 and 3 to 25 N. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 2 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 3 to $0.2F_{ult} = 140$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 3 to 25 N. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 2 to $0.4F_{ult} = 280$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 2 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 2. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 2 and 3 to $0.4F_{ult} = 280$ N. Preload actuators 2 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 2 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 3 to $0.4F_{ult} = 280$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.

- Load lines 1 and 2 to $0.6F_{\text{ult}} = 420$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 2 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 2. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 2 and 3 to $0.6F_{\text{ult}} = 420$ N. Preload actuators 2 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 2 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 3 to $0.6F_{\text{ult}} = 420$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 2 to $0.8F_{\text{ult}} = 560$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 2 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 2. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 2 and 3 to $0.8F_{\text{ult}} = 560$ N. Preload actuators 2 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 2 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Load lines 1 and 3 to $0.8F_{\text{ult}} = 560$ N. Preload actuators 1 and 3 to 25 N each. Maintain actuator loading and initiate the MOOG program to apply simultaneous loads on actuators 1 and 3. Unload both lines to zero.
 - Conduct a post-loading monotonic test on line 2 at large displacements.
- **17:40:** T-bar test performed with data acquisition at 100 Hz.
 - **17:50–18:00:** Centrifuge swing-down and conclusion of the test.

7 Test Results

7.1 Monotonic Load Test - Anchor 1

Figure 11 presents the normalized load–displacement curves for Anchor 1. The peak load recorded during loading through Line 1 ($F_{1,\text{ult}} = 4$ MN at prototype scale) was used for normalization. Displacements were normalized by the anchor diameter ($D = 4.5$ m at prototype scale).

Figure 11: Anchor 1: normalized load displacement curves for monotonic load

Figure 12 shows the load–displacement curve for loading through Line 1, considered the baseline monotonic loading scenario. Excess pore pressures recorded at the top and base of the anchor are also plotted. To allow direct comparison of pore pressure responses, an initial offset was applied, setting the values to zero at the start of loading (ΔPwP in Figure 12b).

An additional curve presents the estimated net anchor displacement at the load application point. This was derived from combined measurements of anchor rotation and translation obtained using laser sensors. The calculation method is documented in a Jupyter notebook (**SW_03_NOTEBOOK.ipynb**). An offset was applied to this curve to align it with the actuator-derived displacement curve at approximately $0.2D$ normalized displacement.

The difference between the actuator-imposed displacement and the anchor movement at the load depth suggests that some actuator travel is needed before effective load transfer occurs. This likely reflects system slack or initial interaction between the mooring line and surrounding clay that must be overcome before the anchor resists the applied load.

Figure 12: Anchor 1: load displacement and excess pore pressure curves for line 1

7.2 Multidirectional Alternating Load Test – Anchor 2

Figure 13 shows the variation of the applied loads on the mooring lines, along with the corresponding excess pore pressure and vertical displacement over model time. The forces were normalized using the baseline monotonic capacity measured for Anchor 1 ($F_{1,ult} = 4$ MN at prototype scale).

Vertical displacements were recorded using laser sensors positioned above the anchor extension, as shown in Figure 8, and were normalized by the anchor diameter ($D = 4.5$ m at prototype scale).

Figure 13: Anchor 2: alternated monotonic load with increasing magnitude, excess pore pressures and vertical displacements response

Figure 14 shows the average vertical displacements of the anchor measured by the lasers at the top of the extension piece (Figure 6c), alongside the applied actuator loads. Loads were normalized by the monotonic capacity of Anchor 1, and displacements were normalized by the anchor diameter.

Figure 14: Anchor 2: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements

7.3 Multidirectional Alternating Load Test – Anchor 3

Figure 15 presents the load–displacement curves for Anchor 3, where loads were applied simultaneously through two mooring lines. The results are shown in terms of the resultant force and displacement, as defined in Figure 9b. Although each mooring line was inclined at 45° to the horizontal, the combined action produced a resultant force with an average inclination of approximately 63° .

Normalized forces exceeded $F/F_{1,ult} = 1.0$ when compared to the baseline capacity of Anchor 1. After the bidirectional loading sequence, a final monotonic pull was applied through Line 2 at 45° inclination. In this case, the anchor showed reduced capacity, plateauing at a load of 2.5 MN, corresponding to $F/F_{1,ult} = 0.63$.

Figure 15: Anchor 3: alternated monotonic load by two lines with increasing magnitude, excess pore pressures and vertical displacements response

Figure 16 summarizes the relationship between the normalized resultant force components and the normalized average vertical displacement of Anchor 3. During the first three cycles, the anchor returned close to its initial position after unloading, with narrow load–unload loops indicating limited permanent deformation. In Cycle 4, larger upward displacements were recorded, reaching approximately $0.4D$. This cycle showed a clear upward trend, resulting in permanent vertical displacement in the pullout direction.

Figure 16: Anchor 3: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements

7.4 Strength Characterization Tests

Figure 17 shows the results of undrained shear strength tests performed on the clay. A T-bar with a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 20 mm (projected area $A = 100 \text{ mm}^2$) was used. Shear strength profiles were derived from displacement measurements by a potentiometer and force data from a load cell mounted on the T-bar.

Additional shear strength measurements were taken after the centrifuge test using a Pilcon Hand Vane Tester (33 mm diameter, 50 mm length), suitable for values up to 30 kPa. This method has previously been used in similar centrifuge test programs (Panchal et al., 2020; Ritchie, 2023).

The results show that undrained shear strength increases with depth, from about 2.5 kPa at the surface to 10 kPa at the base of the suction anchor. The hand vane and T-bar results are in close agreement, indicating consistency between methods.

Figure 17: Undrained shear strength profiles

For the calculations of the undrained shear strength profiles, it was employed the following relationship:

$$s_u = \frac{q}{N_t} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$q = F/A \quad (2)$$

and $N_t = 10.5$ corresponding to the T-bar factor (Stewart and Randolph, 1991).

8 Data sets

The data sets are presented in model scale. The scaling laws applicable to the measured quantities are documented in the centrifuge testing literature (Madabhushi, 2014). Exceptionally, the dataset of the Digital Image Correlation Analysis is already processed and the results are in terms of prototype scale. The data sets consist of raw data obtained from the data logging system, requiring offset corrections to ensure that loads and excess pore pressures start from zero. The files are stored in `.csv` format. Additionally, Jupyter Notebook scripts (`.ipynb`) are provided, which can be used to reproduce the curves and analyses presented in this report.

8.1 Load tests

For the project, the data sets for the loading tests are identified following this structure:

SW_x_xx_xxx_xxxx

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
x	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
xx	Anchor identifier: 1, 2, 3.
xxx	Load type: H(horizontal), V (vertical), I (inclined), M (multidirectional)
xxxx	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_03_1_M_MO corresponds to test 03, on anchor 1, subjected to multidirectional load (M), monotonic (MO).

8.2 T-bar tests

For the T-bar tests, the data sets are identified as follows:

SW_y-yy-yyy

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
y	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
yy	T-bar consecutive identifier: TBAR1, TBAR2, TBAR3.
yyy	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_03 TBAR1 _MO corresponds to centrifuge test 03, T-bar number 1 of type monotonic (MO).

8.3 Data files

The loading tests are organized as follows:

File **SW_03_1_M_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	P180	Pore pressure at the anchor base (kPa)
3	P195	Pore pressure at one diameter depth below the anchor base (kPa)
4	P177	Pore pressure at the top of the anchor (kPa)
5	F_163	Force recorded in mooring line 2 (DaN)
6	D146	Linear laser 1 measurement (mm)
7	D152	Linear laser 2 measurement (mm)
8	D159	Laser sensor measurement in line 1 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
9	D158	Laser sensor measurement in line 2 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
10	D163	Laser sensor measurement in line 3 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
11	F_162	Force recorded in mooring line 1 (DaN)
12	F_109	Force recorded in mooring line 3 (DaN)
13	GTX1	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 1 (mm)
14	GTX2	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 2 (mm)
15	GTX3	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 3 (mm)

Table 5: Description of recorded parameters.

File **SW_03_2_M_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	P141	Pore pressure at the anchor base (kPa)
3	P701	Pore pressure at one diameter depth below the anchor base (kPa)
4	P177	Pore pressure at the top of the anchor (kPa)
5	F_163	Force recorded in mooring line 2 (DaN)
6	D146	Linear laser 1 measurement (mm)
7	D152	Linear laser 2 measurement (mm)
8	D159	Laser sensor measurement in line 1 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
9	D158	Laser sensor measurement in line 2 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
10	D163	Laser sensor measurement in line 3 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
11	F_162	Force recorded in mooring line 1 (DaN)
12	F_109	Force recorded in mooring line 3 (DaN)
13	GTX1	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 1 (mm)
14	GTX2	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 2 (mm)
15	GTX3	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 3 (mm)

Table 6: Description of recorded parameters.

File **SW_03_3_M_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	P174	Pore pressure at the anchor base (kPa)
3	P175	Pore pressure at one diameter depth below the anchor base (kPa)
4	P177	Pore pressure at the top of the anchor (kPa)
5	F_163	Force recorded in mooring line 2 (DaN)
6	D146	Linear laser 1 measurement (mm)
7	D152	Linear laser 2 measurement (mm)
8	D159	Laser sensor measurement in line 1 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
9	D158	Laser sensor measurement in line 2 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
10	D163	Laser sensor measurement in line 3 direction at the anchor extension (mm)
11	F_162	Force recorded in mooring line 1 (DaN)
12	F_109	Force recorded in mooring line 3 (DaN)
13	GTX1	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 1 (mm)
14	GTX2	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 2 (mm)
15	GTX3	Displacement of the actuator in mooring line 3 (mm)

Table 7: Description of recorded parameters.

File **SW_03_2_M_MO_DIC** (prototype scale processed data):

Column	Id	Description
1	Time [m]	Recording time of the camera (s)
2	x_disp [m]	X coordinate of the DIC marker tracked in Blender (m)
3	y_disp [m]	Y coordinate of the DIC marker tracked in Blender (m)

Table 8: Description of recorded parameters for DIC marker tracking.

File **SW_03_3_M_MO_DIC** (prototype scale processed data):

Column	Id	Description
1	Time [m]	Recording time of the camera (s)
2	x_disp [m]	X coordinate of the DIC marker tracked in Blender (m)
3	y_disp [m]	Y coordinate of the DIC marker tracked in Blender (m)

Table 9: Description of recorded parameters for DIC marker tracking.

File **SW_03_TBAR2_MO**

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time (s)
2	FORCE_TBAR	Force recorded by the T-bar load cell (N)
3	DISP_TBAR	Displacement of the T-bar during the test (mm)

Table 10: Description of recorded parameters for the T-bar test.

File **SW_03_TBAR3_MO**

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time (s)
2	FORCE_TBAR	Force recorded by the T-bar load cell (N)
3	DISP_TBAR	Displacement of the T-bar during the test (mm)

Table 11: Description of recorded parameters for the T-bar test.

8.4 Other files

Several water content samples were obtained before and after the centrifuge test (Figure 18), the data file **SW_03_water_content.csv** contains the water content values obtained after the centrifuge test. In addition, the average value of the water content of the clay before consolidation is included (initial).

Figure 18: Water content profiles

File: **SW_03_water_content**

Column	Id	Description
1	Column	Identifier for the sampling location of water content samples
2	Depth (mm)	Depth of the sample (mm)
3	Water_Cont (%)	Measured water content (%)

Table 12: Description of recorded parameters for water content samples.

The geometry of the experimental setup of the loading tests is provided in .DXF files that can be opened in any computed assisted design (CAD) application. The files are identified as follows:

SW_03_TEST_SETUP.dxf

A set of photographs, labeled **PHOTO_1** to **PHOTO_11**, illustrate the main components of the test setup.

References

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